

Effectiveness of Training and Development on the Employees at Fisar Ltd

Raziur Rahman (Author)
PGDM Student

Siva Sivani Institute of Management
Kompally, Secunderabad - 500100, Telangana, India

Supervised under
Kishor Chandra Sahu
Associate Professor

Siva Sivani Institute of Management
Kompally, Secunderabad - 500100, Telangana, India

Abstract:- A company's most valuable asset is its workforce, so understanding them is crucial to success. With the aid of training and development programs, organizations can create a skilled and competent workforce that will maintain a high level of competency and thrive in a dynamic business environment. This research sought to understand the effectiveness of training and development at Fisar Limited in Hyderabad. The study made use of descriptive analysis and analytical research. To collect the primary data, questionnaires were distributed to 50 employees. This included demographic profile and effectiveness of training. According to the findings, Overall training and development have a significant impact on employee performance. It benefits the organization by reducing employee turnover, increasing employee productivity, and contributing to higher financial returns. Factors such as gender, age, work experience, and training schedule have a significant impact on training efficacy. An important element in an organization's success is offering a formal training program for both new and existing employees and analysing the results since it oversees their learning and corrects it promptly. The mode of training and educational credentials must be combined to meet the needs. Organisation needs to identify room for improvement in the areas where training and development are necessary.

Disclaimer: The author's opinions are expressed in this paper, which is the result of professional research. It is not intended to represent the Fisar, its members, or any staff members' official positions or opinions. The author is responsible for any errors. The company name has been modified for research purposes.

Keywords:- Training, Development, Efficiency, Effectiveness, Employee performance, Pharma organization, Human Resources.

I. INTRODUCTION

Training and development are important for any company that wants to retain employees and achieve the best results. Existing companies need to create training and development programs that enable them to acquire the necessary skills and competencies in the organisation. But without skilled labour, companies face poor production problems and low productivity. Training is the formal and systematic modification of behavior through learning which occurs as a

result of education, instruction, development, and planned experience. Development is improving individual performance in their present Roles and preparing them for greater responsibilities in the future (Armstrong 2001).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of this literature review reflects on the effectiveness of training and development and its significance in an organisation. Ananthalakshmi Mahadevan et al. (2019), stated how both on-the-job training and off-the-job training are quantifiably defined led to an understanding of how training mode has a significant impact on employee performance, Sumaiya Shafiq et al. (2017), indicated a strong and positive correlation between an increase in employee performance and training evaluation, depending on the selection of the evaluation criteria, measuring performance knowledge, skill, and attitude against the standard and evaluating the training's content and methods could easily help employees perform better at work. Ashikhube Humphrey Otuko et al. (2013), indicated the effects of training evaluation on employee performance, training content, and training need assessment on employee performance. Tarun Singh (2015), demonstrated on how mean and standard deviation can be helpful in need assessment, and effectiveness of training and development. Philipina Ampomah (2016), showed how training and development can be implemented and its impact on developing policies. Lina Vyas (2004), described as an effective training program is one whose outcomes align with its goals. Training effectiveness is determined by the degree to which the outcome is closer to the objective. Evaluation is the most important method for determining whether or not training is effective. However, other factors, such as learning transfer, the trainer's ability to deliver and trainees' ability to absorb, the institute's and trainers' capacity to recognize and appropriately address trainee needs, and an adequate match between the training package and the trainees' requirements, also have an impact on training's effectiveness. Huque A.S and Vyas L (2008), training effectiveness can be evaluated by looking at trainee performance, evaluation results, and their ability to apply techniques to their jobs. Training effectiveness can also be influenced by trainee characteristics, training design, and contextual factors. Scaduto Anne, Lindsay Douglas & Chiabur S. Dan, (2008), Training effectiveness can also be a function of trainee characteristics, training design and contextual factors. Many organisations are reconsidering their investments in human resource practices such as training as they begin to recognize that the knowledge, skills, and competencies of their

employees give them an advantage that is difficult for competitors to imitate.

III. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

A. The Effectiveness of Training & Development

When a training outcome matches its objectives, it is considered to be effective. The effectiveness of training is determined by the degree to which the outcome is closer to the objective. Evaluation, according to Lina Vyas (2004), is the most important method for determining whether or not training is effective. However, other factors, such as learning transfer, the trainer's ability to deliver and trainees' ability to absorb, the institute's and trainers' ability to recognize needs and appropriately address them, and an adequate match between the training package and trainee requirements, also have an impact on training effectiveness. Huque A.S. and Vyas L. (2008) say that training effectiveness can be measured by looking at trainee performance, evaluation results, and their ability to apply new skills to their jobs. According to Scaduto Anne, Lindsay Douglas, and Chiabur S. Dan (2008), trainee characteristics, training design, and contextual factors can also influence training effectiveness.

B. Model for measuring Training Effectiveness

In this paper, the effectiveness of the training and development has been assessed on the following parameters:

- Curriculum Design
- Satisfaction With Training
- Knowledge Transfer
- Results

IV. OBJECTIVE

To determine the effectiveness of the Training and Development program at Fisar Limited. The study aims to focus on the following objectives in particular:

1. Study and comprehend employees' perceptions towards the organisation's training and development initiatives.

2. Study the effectiveness of training in the organisation.
3. Investigate the factors that determine whether or not training in the organisation is successful.

V. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design and analytical research served as the foundation for this study. The study was conducted on 50 employees from the target population of 59 employees working for an organisation (Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W.1970). This research uses both primary and secondary data for its purposes. Two sections of a self-organized questionnaire were created. The demographic questions are in the first section, and the subjective questions are in the second section. Likert scale was used for subjective questions. The questionnaire was completed by employees of various designations for the purpose of this study.

VI. RESULTS

In this section, results relating to the study are presented in the order of the objectives and the hypotheses.

A. Training effectiveness by Gender

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviations of scores obtained by the employees on measures of perceived training based on curriculum design, satisfaction with training, knowledge transfer, and results with respect to their gender. The arithmetic mean for Curriculum Design (CD) is $\bar{X}=12.0$, Satisfaction with Training (ST) is $\bar{X}=9.0$, Knowledge Transfer (KT) is $\bar{X}=12.0$, Results (R) is $\bar{X}=6.0$. If respondents score above arithmetic mean scores it indicates that effectiveness is more and vice-versa if it is less. In order to determine whether respondents' scores differed significantly, F values were also computed for each subscale.

H0: Gender does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness

Table 1: Training effectiveness by Gender

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
		D.f=1,49				
Curriculum Design	Male	45	18.21	3.11	0.335	0.566
	Female	5	17.40	0.89		
	Total	50	18.13	2.98		
Satisfaction with Training	Male	45	13.73	2.36	0.474	0.495
	Female	5	13.00	1.00		
	Total	50	13.66	2.26		
Knowledge Transfer	Male	45	18.10	2.15	0.012	0.914
	Female	5	18.00	1.87		
	Total	50	18.09	2.10		
Results	Male	45	9.15	1.42	0.146	0.704
	Female	5	9.40	0.54		
	Total	50	9.17	1.36		

$p < 0.1$; $p @ < 0.05$

Table 1, The scores generated by genders based on questions, Employees do not vary in their perceptions about the effectiveness of training according to gender as the F value is less than 1 in all dimensions i.e., Curriculum design, Satisfaction with training, Knowledge transfer, and Results respectively.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that males perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}$ =18.21) than females ($\bar{X}$ =17.40). However, both of them scored above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is more in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that males perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}$ =13.73) than females ($\bar{X}$ =13.00). However, both of them scored above the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that males perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}$ =18.10) than females ($\bar{X}$ =18.00). However, both of them scored above the

expected mean of 12.0. This indicates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that females perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}$ =9.40) than males ($\bar{X}$ =9.15). However, both of them scored above the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is more in this company.

Nevertheless, the null hypothesis is accepted because the F value indicates the mean scores are not statistically significantly varied.

B. Training effectiveness by Age

The employees' mean and standard deviation scores on measures of perceived training based on curriculum effectiveness, satisfaction with training, knowledge transfer, and results based on Age are presented in Table 2. Age defines maturity and understanding of work hence, it was considered here for study. Therefore, it was hypothesized that “**H1:** Age does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness”. Results in this regard are presented in table 2.

Table No. 2 Training effectiveness by Age

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F Df=2,48	Sig
Curriculum Design	21-30	37	17.92	3.33	0.406026	0.66856
	31-40	9	18.88	1.36		
	41-50	4	18.50	1.91		
	Total	50	18.13	2.98		
Satisfaction with Training	21-30	37	13.57	2.54	0.12376	0.883873
	31-40	9	14.00	1.11		
	41-50	4	13.75	1.50		
	Total	50	13.66	2.26		
Knowledge Transfer	21-30	37	18.07	2.19	0.107982	0.897861
	31-40	9	18.33	1.65		
	41-50	4	17.75	2.62		
	Total	50	18.09	2.10		
Results	21-30	37	9.00	1.52	1.316112	0.277678
	31-40	9	9.77	0.44		
	41-50	4	9.50	0.57		
	Total	50	9.17	1.36		

$p < 0.1; p @ < 0.05$

Table 2, The scores generated by age are based on questions. Employees do not vary in their perceptions about the effectiveness of training according to age as the F value is less than 1 in all dimensions i.e., Curriculum design, Satisfaction with training, Knowledge transfer, and Results respectively.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that the age group 31-40 ($\bar{X}$ =18.88) perceived more effectiveness than the age group 41-50 ($\bar{X}$ =18.50), and age group 21-30 ($\bar{X}$ =17.92). Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is more in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that the age group 31-40($\bar{X}$ =14.0) perceived more

effectiveness than the age group 41-50 ($\bar{X}$ =13.75), and age group 21-30 ($\bar{X}$ =13.57). However, all of them scored above the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that the age group 31-40($\bar{X}$ =18.33) perceived more effectiveness than the age group 21-30 ($\bar{X}$ =18.078), and age group 41-50 ($\bar{X}$ =17.75). Although, the score was above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that the age group 31-40 ($\bar{X}$ =9.77) perceived more effectiveness than the age group 41-50 ($\bar{X}$ =9.50), and age group 21-30 ($\bar{X}$ =9.00).

Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is more in this company.

Nevertheless, the null hypothesis is accepted because the F value indicates the mean scores are not statistically significantly varied.

C. Training effectiveness by Education

Education is the most important factor when it comes to upgrading skills, knowledge, and abilities hence, it was pondered here for understanding the training effectiveness. Therefore, it was hypothesized that “**H2**: Education status does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness”. Results in this regard are presented in table 3.

Table No. 3 Training effectiveness by Education

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.	
						Df=1,49	
Curriculum Design	Graduate	37	18.70	1.68	5.267	0.026	
	Postgraduate	13	16.64	4.79			
	Total	50	18.13	2.98			
Satisfaction with Training	Graduate	37	14.18	1.28	8.177	0.006	
	Postgraduate	13	12.28	3.51			
	Total	50	13.66	2.26			
Knowledge Transfer	Graduate	37	18.59	1.53	8.604	0.005	
	Postgraduate	13	16.78	2.83			
	Total	50	18.09	2.10			
Results	Graduate	37	9.37	0.82	3.062	0.086	
	Postgraduate	13	8.64	2.20			
	Total	50	9.17	1.36			

$p < 0.1; p @ < 0.05$

Table 3, Employees vary in their perceptions about the effectiveness of training according to their educational background as the significance of F value is interestingly more in all dimensions i.e., Curriculum design, Satisfaction with training, and Knowledge transfer, except Results.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that Graduates perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=18.70$) than Postgraduates ($\bar{X}=16.64$). However, both scored above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is more in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that Graduates perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=14.18$) than Postgraduates ($\bar{X}=12.28$). However, both scored above the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that Graduates perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=18.59$) than Postgraduates ($\bar{X}=16.78$). However, both scored above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that graduates perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=9.37$) than postgraduates ($\bar{X}=8.64$). However, both scored above the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is more in this company.

Therefore, the F value indicates the mean variation scores are statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted.

D. Training effectiveness by Work Experience

Work experience plays a key role in training as to how fast one can understand a job. This also includes skills such as communication, team-working, and problem-solving which provides employees’ a real advantage. Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation of the representatives’ scores on proportions of seen preparation given curriculum design, satisfaction with training, knowledge transfer, and results by Work Experience. To see if there were any significant differences in respondents’ scores. Therefore, it was hypothesized that “**H3**: Work Experience does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness”. Results in this regard are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Training effectiveness by Work Experience

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
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					Df=3,47	
Curriculum Design	< 3 years	36	17.91	3.37	0.310	0.818
	3-5 years	9	18.66	1.32		
	5-10 years	3	19.33	1.15		
	>10 years	2	18.00	2.82		
	Total	50	18.13	2.98		
Satisfaction with Training	< 3 years	36	13.64	2.59	0.041	0.989
	3-5 years	9	13.77	0.97		
	5-10 years	3	13.33	1.52		
	>10 years	2	14.00	1.41		
	Total	50	13.66	2.26		
Knowledge Transfer	< 3 years	36	18.13	2.23	0.838	0.480
	3-5 years	9	18.11	1.61		
	5-10 years	3	19.00	1.00		
	>10 years	2	16.00	2.82		
	Total	50	18.09	2.10		
Results	< 3 years	36	9.10	1.52	0.393	0.758
	3-5 years	9	9.22	0.97		
	5-10 years	3	10.00	0.00		
	>10 years	2	9.00	0.00		
	Total	50	9.17	1.36		

$p < 0.1; p @ < 0.05$

Table 4, The scores generated by work experience are based on questions. Employees do not vary in their perceptions about the effectiveness of training according to work experience as the F value is less than 1 in all dimensions i.e., Curriculum design, Satisfaction with training, Knowledge transfer, Results respectively.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that work experience of 5-10 years ($\bar{X}=19.33$) perceived more effectiveness followed by work experience holder of 3-5 years ($\bar{X}=18.66$), than work experience of more than 10 years ($\bar{X}=18.00$), and work experience of fewer than 3 years ($\bar{X}=17.91$). Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is more in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that work experience of more than 10 years ($\bar{X}=14.00$) perceived more effectiveness followed by work experience holder of 3-5 years ($\bar{X}=13.77$), than work experience fewer than 3 years ($\bar{X}=13.64$) and work experience of 5-10 years ($\bar{X}=13.33$). However, all of them scored above the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that work experience of 5-10 years ($\bar{X}=19.00$) perceived more effectiveness followed by work experience holder fewer than 3

years ($\bar{X}=18.13$), than work experience of 3-5 years ($\bar{X}=18.11$) and work experience of more than 10 years ($\bar{X}=16.00$). Although, the score was above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that work experience of 5-10 years ($\bar{X}=10.00$) perceived more effectiveness followed by work experience holder of 3-5 years ($\bar{X}=9.22$), than work experience of less than 3 years ($\bar{X}=9.10$) and work experience of more than 10 years ($\bar{X}=9.00$). Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is more in this company.

Nevertheless, the null hypothesis is accepted because the F value indicates the mean scores are not statistically significantly varied.

E. Training effectiveness by Training Schedule

Training Schedule provides a detailed schedule, time frame, outline of activities, and assignment of responsibilities which ideates towards effective work performance hence Table 5 represents the effectiveness of training with reference to training schedule i.e., time period. Therefore, it was hypothesized that “**H4**: Training Schedule does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness”. Results in this regard are presented in table 5.

Table 5: Training effectiveness by Training Schedule

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
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					Df=3,47	
Curriculum Design	Annually	2	19.50	0.70	0.278	0.841
	Every Month	41	18.19	3.21		
	Every Quarter	6	17.33	1.50		
	Half Yearly	1	18.00	0.00		
	Total	50	18.13	2.98		
Satisfaction with Training	Annually	2	15.00	0.00	0.440	0.726
	Every Month	41	13.69	2.44		
	Every Quarter	6	13.33	1.03		
	Half Yearly	1	12.00	0.00		
	Total	50	13.66	2.26		
Knowledge Transfer	Annually	2	16.50	3.53	0.614	0.609
	Every Month	41	18.07	2.17		
	Every Quarter	6	18.83	1.16		
	Half Yearly	1	18.00	0.00		
	Total	50	18.09	2.10		
Results	Annually	2	9.50	0.70	0.199	0.896
	Every Month	41	9.11	1.48		
	Every Quarter	6	9.33	0.51		
	Half Yearly	1	10.00	0.00		
	Total	50	9.17	1.36		

$p < 0.1; p @ < 0.05$

According to Table 5, employees' perceptions of training are the same regardless of their Training Schedule. The scores generated by the effectiveness of the training schedule are based on questions, Employees do not vary in their perceptions about the effectiveness of training according to the training schedule as the F value is less than 1 in all dimensions i.e., Curriculum design, Satisfaction with training, Knowledge transfer, Results respectively.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that the training schedule conducted annually ($\bar{X}=19.50$) perceived more effectiveness followed by the training schedule every month ($\bar{X}=18.19$), than training schedule for half yearly ($\bar{X}=18.00$) and training organised every quarter ($\bar{X}=17.33$). Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is more in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that the training schedule conducted Annually ($\bar{X}=15.00$) was perceived as more effective followed by the training schedule organised every month ($\bar{X}=13.69$), than the training schedule every quarter ($\bar{X}=13.33$) and, training schedule half yearly ($\bar{X}=12.00$). However, all of them scored above the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that the training schedule conducted during every quarter ($\bar{X}=18.83$) was perceived as more effective followed by the training schedule held during every month ($\bar{X}=18.07$), than the training schedule organised half yearly ($\bar{X}=18.00$) and, training schedule presided annually ($\bar{X}=16.50$). Although, the score was above the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that the training schedule conducted half yearly ($\bar{X}=10.00$) was perceived as more effective followed by the training schedule organised annually ($\bar{X}=9.50$), than the training schedule of every quarter ($\bar{X}=9.33$) and training schedule managed every month ($\bar{X}=9.11$). Although, the scores are above the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is more in this company.

Nevertheless, the null hypothesis is accepted because the F value indicates the mean scores are not statistically significantly varied.

➤ *Training effectiveness by Training Mode*

The mode of training provides simultaneous learning along with regular work. Hence, it ensures the effectiveness of training and development. Therefore, it was hypothesized that “**H5:** Training Mode does not influence Curriculum Effectiveness”. Results in this regard are presented in table 6.

Table No. 6: Training effectiveness by Training Mode

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
				Df=2,48	

Curriculum Design	Both	42	18.39	2.32	11.024	0.000
	Off the Job	2	10.00	8.48		
	On the Job	6	19.00	1.09		
	Total	50	18.13	2.98		
Satisfaction with Training	Both	42	13.95	1.75	8.607	0.001
	Off the Job	2	8.00	7.07		
	On the Job	6	13.50	1.37		
	Total	50	13.66	2.26		
Knowledge Transfer	Both	42	18.39	1.82	3.773	0.030
	Off the Job	2	15.00	5.65		
	On the Job	6	17.00	2.00		
	Total	50	18.09	2.10		
Results	Both	42	9.27	0.95	10.766	0.000
	Off the Job	2	5.50	4.94		
	On the Job	6	9.66	0.51		
	Total	50	9.17	1.36		

$p < 0.1$; $p @ < 0.05$

Table 6 shows the mean and standard deviation scores of the representatives on proportions of seen preparation in light of curriculum design, satisfaction with training, knowledge transfer, and results by Training Mode.

With regards to Curriculum Design (CD), it was found that on the job perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=19.00$) followed by both the methods i.e., on the job and off the job ($\bar{X}=18.39$) than off the job ($\bar{X}=16.64$). Conversely, off the job scored below the expected mean of 12.0. This indicates CD is less effective in off the job training mode in this company.

With regards to Satisfaction with Training (ST), it was found that both on the job and off the job training methods ($\bar{X}=13.95$) perceived more effectiveness followed by on the job ($\bar{X}=13.50$) than off the job training mode ($\bar{X}=8.0$). Contrarily, off the job method score was below the expected mean of 9.0. This indicates ST is more in off the job training mode in this company.

With regards to Knowledge Transfer (KT), it was found that both on the job and off the job training methods perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=18.39$) followed by on-the-job mode ($\bar{X}=17.00$) and off the job ($\bar{X}=15.00$). However, all scored above the expected mean of 12.0. This illustrates KT is more in this company.

With regards to Results (R), it was found that on the job perceived more effectiveness ($\bar{X}=9.66$) followed by both the methods i.e., on the job and off the job ($\bar{X}=9.27$), off the job effectiveness is lower ($\bar{X}=5.5$). Contrariwise, off the job scored below the expected mean of 6.0. This indicates Results (R) is less effective in off the job training mode in this company.

Because of this, the F value indicates that the mean variation scores are statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected.

VII. DISCUSSIONS

With regards to gender, Males perceived training to be more effective than females. Al-Swidi and Al Yahya (2017) also supported males who were found to be different from

females in their perception of the effectiveness of training and development as per their learning style. Wood (1987) showed that mixed gender groups performed better than the same gender group. Richard et al (2004) have observed an inverted U-shaped relationship between management group gender heterogeneity and productivity, with moderately heterogeneous management groups exhibiting better performance than gender homogeneous management groups.

Regarding age, Employees in the middle age group are more pleased with the organization's training and development programmes. The F value also suggested that effectiveness doesn't vary according to the age. Similarly, Lesch et al (2011) found that older adults have greater difficulty than younger adults in comprehending warning symbols and that accident scenario training improves comprehension. Organisations nominate employees of different age groups for the training programs whereas during training younger people learn faster than older people owing to various reasons like enthusiasm, exploration etc. Therefore, Trainers should pay more attention towards older age trainees when it comes to their learnings.

Effectiveness of training with respect to education varies in the organisation. Graduates were found more effective towards training than post-graduates as the F value is also statistically significant. Mathieu, et al (1992) also discovered the implication of education levels that influence individuals' scores on the learning measure. Graduates are interested in adapting and upgrading their knowledge, skills, and abilities as this could be a possible reason why graduates are more inclined towards training and development than post-graduates, as it shapes their career growth.

According to employee work experience, training effectiveness was complacent. This also supports the study by Heyes, and Stuart, (1996) on the influence of workplace practices and employees' experiences on training effectiveness. As work experience provides a pathway towards comprehension of the training it is essential for trainers in the organisation to provide guidance to employees with less experience.

Training schedule/calendar was found standardised in the organisation, as the F value is also not statistically significant. The standardised training schedule/calendar in the organisation lends credence to the study conducted by Cromwell, and Kolb (2004). Organisations having proper training schedules as per the activities, time frames and responsibilities tend to be more effective. When the training is conducted every month as per the requirements, the effectiveness of training is likely to be more than training conducted annually.

The mode of training has a significant effect. According to the findings, on-the-job is perceived as a more effective mode of training. Alipour, Salehi, & Shahnava, (2009) also inquired about the effectiveness of on-the-job training. As off-the-job training reduces exposure to work environment and feedback is poor because of no real time interaction among trainers and trainees. Therefore, Training mode determines the effectiveness of training.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

- With regards to qualification, most of the employees are graduates, i.e., 74%, and postgraduates, i.e., 26%, so they are qualified and educated. However, focusing on either providing post-graduation study or hiring post-graduation candidates will bring more experience into the business, which will help it grow and make better strategic decisions.
- The personal growth of an employee and the period of time they stay with the company will be significantly influenced by both on-the-job and off-the-job training.
- Technology must allow for improvisation. The Company must keep up with the ever-evolving technology. For better performance and productivity, it's important to stay current with technology.
- Training should be more realistic because many employees do not understand their jobs. As a result, it is recommended that they receive it in a way that improves their comprehension.
- The training program should be practical, based on the organization's strategy, and realistic, so organizations should make an effort to ensure this. As a result, the organization ought to concentrate on locating the specific areas in which actual training requirements have emerged. Based on authoritative procedure, preparing projects ought to be executed.

IX. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Since the researcher only had a limited amount of time to conduct the study, it was not possible to conduct a comprehensive and in-depth investigation.
- The study's sample size was 50, so it cannot be considered conclusive.
- Constraint on Perception: Employees frequently tend to overestimate their skills after training and underestimate them before training in order to justify their involvement in the training program. This illustrates how challenging it is to correctly evaluate or measure a training program's effectiveness.

- One of the most important contexts for a training program is a return on investment (ROI), which was not tested in this study.

X. CONCLUSION

Training and development are critical to improving employee performance as it creates a highly skilled workforce and supports employee personal growth. This study was conducted to examine the effectiveness of training and development on employee performance at Fisar Limited. The study found that training and development have a significant impact on employee performance. Training and development programs delivered in an in-depth format have led to improved organizational performance, productivity, and financial returns. Employee perceptions of the training and development programs in place in the organization are positive. They felt that training and development contributed to their personal growth and encouraged them to be enthusiastic about their work. The effectiveness of training with respect to gender, age, work experience, training schedule is decisive according to the study. Providing a formal training program for new and existing employees and evaluating results is a key factor in the success of an organization as it manages their learning and corrects it in a timely manner. After analysing the survey results, it is concluded that the mode of training needs a blend, as well as education qualifications to be assimilated as per requirement. Organisation needs to identify room for improvement in the areas where training and development are required.

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AUTHOR DETAILS

Raziur Rahman

Pursuing PGDM HR, passionate about changing trends in the business environment. The most adored aspect of human resource management being training and development. Previously self-published poetry book "The Taste of Ink" on Amazon sobriquet under Raseen Rahil. Feel free to provide any valuable feedback or connect with me through social media: Instagram: @bottleofinkets , Email: raziurahman@gmail.com